

Properties and structural performance of KD-II SiC fiber with different temperature in air and argon atmosphere

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1.XRD analysis of fibers treated at different temperature in air

Fig.1 XRD pattern of product from SiC fibers without heat treatment and at different temperature in air: (a) without heat treatment, (b) 800°C, (c) 1000°C, (d) 1200°C, (e) 1400°C, (f) 1500°C.

2. Surface morphology of as-received SiC fibers

Fig.2 Surface morphology of SiC fibers without heat treatment

3. Surface morphology of fibers treated at 1500 °C

Fig.3 Surface morphology of SiC fibers with heat treatment at 1500°C in different atmosphere : (a) air; (b) argon

4. Summary

The high temperature exposure for KD-II continuous silicon carbide fibers was carried out at 800 °C, 1000 °C, 1200 °C, 1400 °C and 1500 °C for 1 h in air and argon atmosphere. XRD results showed that strong peaks from silica oxide could be observed when temperature exceeded 1400°C, indicating that the silica oxide began to crystallize on the surface of the fiber. However, no silica formation was observed from XRD results for different temperature heat treatment in argon atmosphere. SEM micrographs revealed that the silica oxide layer was formed on the surface of SiC fiber at 1500°C in air and the crack of the silica oxide layer was observed. But in argon atmosphere, the smooth surface was observed at all temperatures, suggesting that the formation of silica was prevented due to the presence of argon. From the above analysis, it can be seen that the surface structure of SiC fibers is significantly changed at high temperature in air .